

Pyridazines. Part V.¹ Action of Grignard Reagents on 4,6-Diaryl- and 6-Aryl-4,5-dihydro- and 6-Aryl-pyridazin-3(2H)-ones

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4,6-Diaryl-4,5-dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-ones reacted with phenylmagnesium bromide to give the corresponding 4,6-diaryl-3-phenylpyridazines. With benzyl-magnesium bromide they gave the corresponding 5-benzyl-4,6-diaryl-4,5-dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-ones. 6-Aryl-4,5-dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-ones, however reacted with *o*-methoxyphenylmagnesium bromide to give 6-aryl-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-3,3-di(*o*-methoxyphenyl)-pyridazine, whereas with *p*-tolylmagnesium bromide, they gave 6-aryl-3-*p*-tolylpyridazines. 6-Aryl-pyridazin-3(2H)-ones reacted with arylmagnesium halides to give the 4,6-diaryl- or 4,6-diaryl-4,5-dihydro-pyridazin-3(2H)-ones, whereas with benzyl-magnesium chloride, 6-aryl-4,5-dibenzyl-4,5-dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-ones were exclusively obtained.

IN continuation of the previous study on the action of Grignard reagents on 6-aryl-4,5-dihydro- and 6-arylpyridazin-3(2H)-ones,² the 4,6-diaryl-4,5-dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-ones (3) and (4) were prepared by heating β -aroyl- α -aryl-propionic acids (1) and (2) with hydrazine hydrate in *n*-butanol. The β -aryl structure assigned to these acids² was established by reducing (1) to the corresponding butyric acid and its structure substantiated by n.m.r. spectroscopy.

magnesium bromide to give the corresponding 4,6-diaryl-3-phenylpyridazines (5) and (6), respectively. Their structure is inferred from their i.r. spectra which are devoid of $\gamma_{C=O}$ or γ_{NH} and from the similarity of their u.v. spectra to those of 3,6-diarylpyridazines. However, with benzylmagnesium chloride the products are most probably 4,6-diaryl-5-benzyl-4,5-dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-ones (9) and (10), respectively, since their i.r. spectra show $\gamma_{C=O}$ and γ_{RH} (Table 2). Their electronic spectra are very

Action of Grignard Reagents on 4,6-diaryl-4,5-dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-ones: 4,6-Diaryl-4,5-dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-ones (3) and (4) reacted with phenyl

similar to those of the corresponding 4,6-diaryl-4,5-dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-ones (3) and (4). Four possible structures (A, B, C and D), however, can be assigned to these products.

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I.r., u.v. and n.m.r. spectral data are shown in the experimental part.

Structure (A) was excluded from its M.W. which was found to be 398(MS). Structure (C) was excluded from the n.m.r. spectra of (9) which does not show the signal for an olefinic proton. The

presence of coupling in the spectrum excludes structure (B) and supports structure (D) (see experimental).

The reaction appears to proceed by the dehydrogenation of (3) and (4) to (7) and (8), respectively, followed by addition of one molecule of benzylmagnesium chloride.

The interaction between (3) and *o*-methoxyphenylmagnesium bromide, however, gave rise to a product which was proved by m.p. and mixed m.p. to be (7).

Action of o-Methoxyphenyl- and p-Tolylmagnesium Bromide on 6-Aryl-4, 5-dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-ones (11), (12) and (13): 6-Aryl-4, 5-dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-ones² reacted with *o*-methoxyphenylmagnesium bromide to give 6-aryl-2, 3, 4, 5-tetrahydro-3, 3-di(*o*-methoxyphenyl)-pyridazines (14), (15) and (16), respectively. The presence of γ_{NH} and absence of $\gamma_{\text{C=O}}$ in their i.r. spectra (Table 2) suggests the possibility of assigning structures E or F to the products.

Structure (E) was, however, favoured by the n.m.r. spectra of compounds (14) and (15) (see experimental).

The reaction appears to take place according to scheme (2) without ring opening since when the intermediate Grignard complex (17; Ar = 3, 4(Me)₂C₆H₃, Ar' = *o*-MeOC₆H₄) was refluxed before decomposition with an excess of Me₂SO₄ the product was proved

to be (18) and not (19) from the following evidence: a) percentage of NCH₃ and OCH₃, b) identity with an authentic sample, prepared by methylation of (14) with dimethyl sulphate.

The reaction of (11), (12) and (13) with *p*-tolylmagnesium bromide proceeded, however, normally to give 6-aryl-3-*p*-tolylpyridazines (20), (21) and (22), respectively. The i.r. spectra of the products are devoid of $\gamma_{\text{C=O}}$ and γ_{NH} (Table 2).

Action of Grignard Reagents on 6-Aryl-pyridazin-3(2H)-ones (23), (24) and (25): The pyridazines were prepared by the dehydrogenation of the corresponding 3-pyridazinones with bromine in acetic acid and subjected to the action of Grignard reagents. (23) gave with phenyl-, *o*-methoxyphenyl-, α -naphthyl-, and *p*-methoxyphenylmagnesium bromide, 4, 6-diaryl-4, 5-dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-ones (26a, b, c and d), respectively (Table 3). The structure assign-

ned to these products was inferred from analytical data and i.r. spectra (presence of $\gamma_{\text{C=O}}$ and γ_{NH}), and rigidly established by the identity of (26a) with an authentic sample prepared by heating β -(3, 4-dimethylbenzoyl)- α -phenylpropionic acid (36) with hydrazine hydrate (Scheme 3). The α -phenyl structure assigned to (36) was based on the formation of a pyryllium salt, when its alcoholic solution with

Scheme (2)

(19); Ar = 3,4(Me)₂C₆H₃; Ar' = o-MeO-C₆H₄

salicylaldehyde was treated with HCl gas.^{3,4} The u.v. spectra of the products (26a, b, c and d) are identical to those of the corresponding 6-aryl-4, 5-dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-ones,² indicating that they all have the same chromophoric system.

- (20); Ar = 3,4-dimethylphenyl
 (21); Ar = 2,4-dimethylphenyl
 (22); Ar = 2,5-dimethylphenyl

Similarly, (24) reacted with phenyl- and *o*-methoxyphenyl-magnesium bromide to give (27a and b), respectively. The structure of these compounds was based on similar lines. The same reaction occurred between the pyridazine (25) and *o*-methoxyphenylmagnesium bromide to give the pyridazinone (28b). However, with phenyl and α -naphthylmagnesium bromide, the products from (25) appeared to possess a pyridazin-3(2H)-one structure (29a and c; Ar = 2,5(Me)₂C₆H₃), respectively, rather than the dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-one structure (28a

and c), as indicated from their i.r. and u.v. spectra (Table 3).^{2,5}

However, when the pyridazin-3(2H)-ones (23), (24) and (25) were allowed to react with benzylmagnesium chloride they added two molecules of the Grignard reagent to give 6-aryl-4, 5-dibenzyl-4, 5-dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-ones (30), (31) and (32) respectively. The other possible structures (33) and (34) were excluded, since the M.W. of 31 (MS) was found to be 382. The structure assigned to the products was inferred from their i.r. spectra (presence of $\gamma_{C=O}$ and γ_{NH} sh.) and their u.v. spectra which are very similar to those of (26), (27) and (28), respectively (Table 3). Moreover, the structure of (31) was further substantiated by its n.m.r. spectrum (Table 3). The reaction appears to proceed through the intermediate formation of (29; Ar' = Ph-CH₂-) followed by the 1,4-addition of a second molecule of benzylmagnesiumchloride to the $-C=C-C=O$ system.

Synthesis of 6-Aryl-4-Benzyl-Pyridazin-3(2H)ones (37a, b and c): These were prepared by the condensation of the 4, 5-dihydro-pyridazin-3(2H)-ones (11), (12) and (13) with benzaldehyde in the presence of alc. KOH.

The pyridazine-3(2H)-one structure of the products was inferred from their i.r. spectra which show $\gamma_{C=O}$ and a broad band in the 3 μ region characteristic of

(23); Ar = 3,4(Me)₂C₆H₃ (26); Ar = 3,4(Me)₂C₆H₃

(24); Ar = 2,4(Me)₂C₆H₃ (27); Ar = 2,4(Me)₂C₆H₃

(25); Ar = 2,5(Me)₂C₆H₃ (28); Ar = 2,5(Me)₂C₆H₃

a; Ar' = Ph

c; Ar' = α -naphthyl

b; Ar' = \underline{o} -MeOC₆H₄

d; Ar' = \underline{p} -MeOC₆H₄

(30); Ar = 3,4(Me)₂C₆H₃

(31); Ar = 2,4(Me)₂C₆H₃

(32); Ar = 2,5(Me)₂C₆H₃

(33); Ar = 2,4(Me)₂C₆H₃

(34); Ar = 2,4(Me)₂C₆H₃

(35); Ar = 2,4(Me)₂C₆H₃

(36); Ar = 3,4(Me)₂C₆H₃

(26a)

Scheme (3)

γ_{NH} of pyridazin-3(2H)-ones.² The u.v. spectra of these products are identical with those of the corresponding 6-aryl-pyridazin-3(2H)-ones,³ (Table 4). The

ing 4-(3,4-dimethylphenyl)-2-benzylidene-but-3-enoic acid lactone (38) with hydrazine hydrate.

a; Ar = 3,4(Me)₂C₆H₃

b; Ar = 2,4(Me)₂C₆H₃

c; Ar = 2,5(Me)₂C₆H₃

structure was further substantiated by the identity of (37a) with an authentic sample, prepared by heat-

Experimental

I.r. (KBr) and u.v. spectra were measured using Perkin-Elmer infracord Models 137 and 337 and a Carl Zeiss Spectro-photometer type PMQII, respectively. N.m.r. spectra were measured with Varian 60A.

α , γ -di (3,4-Dimethylphenyl) butyric acid: The keto-acid (1) (4 g) was reduced by refluxing with zinc

(38); Ar = 3,4(Me)₂C₆H₃

(37a)

TABLE 1

Cmpd.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Found %			Formula	Required %			i.r. cm ⁻¹	
			C	H	N		C	H	N	γ_{NH}	$\gamma_{C=O}$
(3)	168-9†	80	78.3	7.2	9.2	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O	78.4	7.2	9.1	3400-3225	1664
(4)	158-9†	72	78.95	7.2	9.3	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O	78.4	7.2	9.1	3200-3080	1665
(7)	235-6@	90	78.5	6.65	9.2	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O	78.9	7.6	9.2	3130-2850 (br.)	1640
(8)	185-6*	90	78.9	6.3	9.25	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O	78.9	7.6	9.2	br. band peaked at 2930-2860	1650

TABLE 2

Cmpd.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Found %			Formula	Required %			i.r. cm ⁻¹		u.v. $\lambda_{max}nm \epsilon$
			C	H	N		C	H	N	γ_{NH}	$\gamma_{C=O}$	
(5)	120-3*	60	85.3	6.9	7.9	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₂	85.7	6.6	7.7			280 35500
(6)	148*	40	85.5	6.7	7.7	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₂	85.7	6.6	7.7			260 14600
(9)†	164-5*	53	81.25	7.3	7.3	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ N ₂ O	81.8	7.1	7.1	3200	1680	297 17400
(10)	200*	41	81.7	7.2	7.6	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ N ₂ O	81.8	7.1	7.1	3200	1760	270 11400
(14)†	191-2*	38	77.6	7.0	6.6	C ₂₈ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂	78.0	7.05	7.0	3450		280 24900
(15)†	172*	30	77.9	7.5	6.7	C ₂₈ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂	78.0	7.05	7.0	3400		273 12500
(16)	176-7*	30	78.3	7.2	7.4	C ₂₈ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂	78.0	7.05	7.0	3420		273 12100
(20)	180-1†	60	83.1	6.6	10.5	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂	83.2	6.6	10.2			290 31100
(21)	111†	55	82.7	6.65	9.4	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂	83.2	6.66	10.2			275 26300
(22)	114-5*	55	83.15	6.3	9.4	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂	83.2	6.6	10.2			275 26000

* From methanol, † from cyclohexane, ‡ from ethanol, @ from acetone.

N.m.r. spectrum of compound (9) showed signals at τ 3(11 H, m), 6.32 (1 H, s), 6.42 (1 H, t), 7.1 (2H, m) and 7.72 (12 H, d). Consequently structure (C) was excluded because the spectrum does not contain a signal for olefinic protons. Structure (D) is more probable because in structure (B) no coupling is expected between the aliphatic protons. The n.m.r. spectra of compounds (14) and (15) showed one signal at τ 6.63 (s, 2MeO), which indicated that the two *o*-MeO-C₆H₄ groups are attached to the same carbon atom, and signals at τ 7.12 (t, CH₂) and 7.7 (t, CH₂), and at 7.1 (t, CH₂) and 7.8 (t, CH₂)(A₂X₂ system; -CH₂-CH₂), respectively, the upfield signal is partially hidden under that for the two Me₂C₆H₃ groups, which appeared at τ 7.78 and 7.72 (6 H, s), respectively. This indicated that structure (E) for both compounds is more probable than structure (F).

TABLE 3

Cmpd.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Found %			Formula	Required %			i.r. cm ⁻¹		u.v.	
			C	H	N		C	H	N	γ_{NH}	$\gamma_{C=O}$	$\lambda_{max}nm$	ϵ
26a	170*	47	77.8	6.4	10.0	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	77.7	6.5	10.1	3250(sh.)	1665	293	19500
26b	165-7*	41	74.3	6.8	8.7	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	74.0	6.5	9.1	3290(sh.)	1675	290	19900
26c	202@	43	81.0	6.2	8.9	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O	80.5	6.1	8.5	3210, 3100(sh.)	1670	225	94900
26d*	162*	40	73.55	6.7	8.55	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	74.0	6.5	9.1	3120, 3080(sh.)	1665	290	19100
27a	142-3*	50	77.8	6.7	10.3	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	77.7	6.5	10.1	3200, 3100(sh.)	1665	275	13000
27b	170-1*	36	73.9	6.7	9.6	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	74.0	6.5	9.1	3250	1665	273	14900
28b	179-80*	42	73.7	6.35	8.25	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	74.0	6.5	9.1	3250	1670	270	12*50
29a	189-90@	41	78.0	6.0	9.7	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	78.2	5.8	10.1	3050-2860+(bt.)	1650	255†	17300
29c	240-1*	40	80.85	5.8	8.2	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	80.95	5.7	8.6	3250-2950(br.)	1670, 220†	74300	
30	179-80*	38	81.5	6.9	7.2	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₂ O	81.6	6.85	7.3	3180, 3090(sh.)	1665	295	17300
29c	240-1	40	80.85	5.8	8.2	C ₂₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	80.95	5.7	8.6	3250-2950(br.)	1670, 220	74300	
31§	166-7*	38	81.5	6.9	7.2	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₂ O	81.6	6.85	7.3	3220, 3100(sh)	1675	275	13400
32	144*	44	81.4	6.8	6.95	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₂ O	81.6	6.85	7.3	3200, 3090(sh)	1660	275	12100

* from methanol, † from ethanol, ‡ from cyclohexane

@ This doublet is attributed to Fermi resonance, which is observed in the case of 6-aryl-pyridazin-3(2H)-ones.²

† 4,5-Dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-ones are known to absorb at a longer wavelength (270-90 nm).

‡ The n.m.r. spectrum of (31) shows a signal at τ 7.2 (m, 6p)

|| The sharp band (sh.) is characteristic of 6-aryl-4,5-dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-ones.

+ The broad band is characteristic of 6-aryl-pyridazin-3(2H)-ones.^{2,5}

amalgam (5 g) and a mixture of conc. hydrochloric acid (10 ml) and water (10 ml) for 3 hrs. The ethereal extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, then distilled off. The

TABLE 4

Cmpd	M.p. °C	Yield	Found%			Formula	Required%			i.r. cm ⁻¹			u.v.	
			C	H	N		C	H	N	ν_{NH}	$\nu_{C=O}$	λ_{max}/nm	ϵ	
37a	153-4	60	78.35	6.6	9.1	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	78.6	6.25	9.65	3050-2857 (br)	1650	260	26,000	
37b	155-6	60	78.4	6.5	10.2	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	78.6	6.25	9.65	br. peaked at 2940	1650	255	18,750	
37c	153-4	52	78.8	6.4	8.9	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	78.6	6.25	9.65	br., sub- maxima at 1940, 2857	1640	250	19,000	
38	137* (yellow)	80	82.8	5.9		C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₂	82.6	5.90			1742	—	—	

* From ethanol.

oily residue solidified when triturated with few drops of *n*-hexane. It was recrystallised from *n*-hexane to give α , γ -di(3,4-dimethylphenyl) butyric acid*, m.p. 79°-80° (Found: C = 81.4; H = 8.1. C₂₀H₂₄O₂ requires C = 81.0; H = 8.2); yield 62%.

4, 6-Diaryl-4-5-dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-ones (3) and (4): The suspension of β -aroyl, α -arylpropionic acids (1) and (2) (0.01 mol) in *n*-butanol (30 ml) was treated with hydrazine hydrate (98%) (1.5 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hrs, then left to cool. The precipitated solid was filtered off and washed with ether, then crystallised from a suitable solvent to give (3) and (4) (Table 1).

4, 6-Diaryl-pyridazin-3(2H)-ones (7) and (8): Bromine (0.4 ml) was added dropwise to a vigorously stirred solution of (3) and (4) (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (40 ml). The stirred reaction mixture was warmed (60°-70°) on a water-bath for 3 hrs and left to cool. The crystals which precipitated on dilution with water were filtered off and triturated with conc. ammonium hydroxide, filtered off, washed with water and crystallised from a suitable solvent (Table 1).

Reaction of 4, 6-Diaryl (3) and (4)- and 6-Aryl (11), (12) and (13)-4, 5-dihydropyridazin-3(2H)-ones with Grignard reagents: The powdered pyridazin-3-one (0.01 mol) was added portionwise to the solution of arylmagnesium bromide (0.03 mol) in ether (50 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 3 hrs, cooled, decomposed with ice-cold dilute HCl, then worked up as usual.† The products were crystallised from suitable solvents (Table 2).

Action of Grignard Reagents on 6-Aryl pyridazin-3(2H)-ones (23), (24) and (25): The suspension of (23), (24), or (25) in dry ether (0.01 mol) was added

* Its n.m.r. spectrum showed signals at τ 3.0 (*m*, ArH), 6.5 (*t*, α -CH), 7.6 (*m*, β -CH₂), and 7.82 (*s*, ArMe and ArCH₃). The alternative structure for this acid would not give a signal at τ 6.5(*t*).

† In case of the reaction of (4) with PhMgBr, the reaction mixture was cooled with ice, for one hr, and decomposed with ice-cold ammonium chloride solution.

portionwise to the solution of arylmagnesium bromide (0.03 mol) in dry ether (50 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 6-8 hrs, and worked up as usual. The ethereal extract was evaporated to dryness and the residue triturated with few drops of methanol, cooled and filtered off. The products were crystallised from suitable solvents (Table 3).

4-Benzyl-pyridazin-3(2H)-ones (37a, b and c): The warm solution of (11), (12) and (13) (6 g) in ethanol (30 ml) was treated with a 4% alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution (75 ml). Benzaldehyde (3 ml) was then added portionwise with continuous shaking. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hrs on a boiling water-bath, cooled, and then diluted with cold water. The precipitated solid was filtered off, washed with water then crystallised from suitable solvents to give (37a, b and c) (Table 4).

Compound (37a) was identical with the product obtained by refluxing 2-benzal-4-(3,4-dimethylphenyl) but-3-enoic lactone (38) (0.5g) with hydrazine hydrate (1 ml) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) and conc. hydrochloric acid (20ml) for 2 hrs. The lactone (38) was obtained by heating *p*-(3,4-dimethylbenzoyl) propionic acid with benzaldehyde (5g.) in acetic anhydride (5 ml) and anhydrous sodium acetate (5g.) on a boiling water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ h. (Table 4).

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